

Plant Disease detection by image classification using Neural Networks

*Ms. Neha Singh, Assistant Professor,
singh.neha773@gmail.com, Indrashil
University, Rajpur, Kadi*

*Dr. Sumit Chaudhary, Associate
Professor, drsumitchaudhary@gmail.com,
Indrashil University, Rajpur, Kadi*

Abstract- In crop monitoring system recognition of Plant disease is a crucial part. Various agriculture issues were always solved by various techniques of Computer vision and deep learning (DL). This paper help in detecting disease in plant leaves with the help of localization and classification. An architecture which includes Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) using TensorFlow object detection framework. Models will be trained and then tested in a controlled environment using proper dataset which help in detecting plant disease in a particular environment.

Keywords: Plant Disease, CNN, Neural Networks, image classification

I. INTRODUCTION

By making better decision than other contenders a successful business can be achieved and it also applies to the agriculture sector. In the field of agriculture with the latest technologies like artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML), farmers can have crucial data, information and tools which help in taking good decision, improve efficiency and also help in reducing food waste, providing better environmental state. So here details of professional ways in the field of agriculture which are of great use and providing good solutions with the use of AI and ML techniques.

A. DIGITAL FARMING

“By supporting the key points of farming & its management, digital farming is helping in increasing

crop production as by providing decision making with good data insights”

In food and biofuel sector, crop production and management play an important part and where Machine learning and artificial intelligence improves the way growers contribute.

Every year farmers and growers take several complex decisions that affect their feasibility, possibility, and their profits. Using ML and AI based applications which are generally based on sensors, farmers can predict and evaluate crop quality, plant identification, plant disease detection, weed detection which was not possible earlier.

B. YIELD PREDICTION AND QUALITY ASSESSMENT

By using ML application, farmer can access or can log in some customized platform on their smartphones or tablet and can have the information on any assessment like harvestable period of any crop or the care to be taken for any crop can be measured or predicted.

Also, by using various technologies such as image analysis or classification, plants or crop can be evaluated before as well as after harvesting for checking required characteristics, any damage or any other factors that can affect crop price or production.

C. SPECIES IDENTIFICATION

So many plants have identical leaf structure or composition with same colors and shapes, which makes it very complex or difficult task for a human eye to identify it. Therefore, nowadays farmers can easily depend on Machine learning and Artificial

intelligence to identify or to find out complex and difficult pattern to do plant identification and weed specification. This type of technology or application can help in saving farmer's time and can increase the productivity of crops.

D. PLANT DISEASE

To recognize or to identify weed species or crop & plant disease i.e., which plant is healthy or which one is infected with some kind of disease by bacteria or virus, ML technique like image processing, image classification help farmers to depend on ML based tools.

Mechanical devices such as robots can be trained to be enabled to identify weeds or infected plants and can help to pull out those infected species from the fields which can be of great help in protecting fields from pesticides as well as saving time and money.

Moreover, these ML based applications can provide timely diagnosis of disease and also providing good treatment plan for the same. Also, it can help all those organizations that produce plant disease treatment products or variants to serve their customer in a better & effective way.

REAL-WORLD USE CASE

Figure 1. Real Case
how model can work

ML applications can help the farmers to click the photograph of their diseased plant or crop and they can get accurate output or diagnosed result as well as product recommendations.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

In Indian economic sector, agriculture plays a very important role. Latest technology and automation in the field of agriculture is a significant concern which can make this sector highly developed and emerging all over the world. With the increase in the number of populations of the country demand of food as well as unemployment is also increasing. Therefore, the traditional methods of agriculture were that much not enough to manage the demand. Thus, new technology-based methods were introduced. Such new techniques or applications will be more convenient for fulfilling food demand as well as give employment to many people. Such technology has been the name of new revolution in the agriculture sector. Also, in farming important role is played by climatic conditions such as rainfall, temperature and humidity. The cause of climate changes includes deforestation and pollution which make it difficult for farmers to make choice for soil preparation and harvesting. For proper growth of any crop, it requires some nutrients like nitrogen(N), phosphorous(P) and potassium(K). Deficiency of these three main nutrients can result in poor quality of crop. Protecting plant or crop from weed play a crucial part in agriculture lifecycle as if it is not done properly it can lead to damaging the plant and will absorb all the nutrients from the soil and can soil deficiency. Artificial Intelligence work in agriculture field and many researches are going on in that area. From the beginning stage only scholars and researchers are focusing on Artificial Intelligence techniques for better management and productivity. Therefore, in this sector stakeholders

can have major role in creating value for business. In creating multi-disciplinary agriculture domain, machine learning has emerged with technologies like big data, data science and other high performance computing techniques. Also, many researchers or scholars have done comprehensive review of research done in machine learning for agriculture production. The work done can be classified as (a) crop management (b) livestock management which consists of animal welfare and livestock production (c) soil management (d) water management. From the presented papers or articles, it can be observed how agriculture industry is getting benefits and other advantages from machine learning. Artificial intelligence industry helps by applying machine learning techniques to farm management system.

III. PROPOSED WORK

Most of the plant disease prediction techniques are based on the concept of deep learning. Convolutional Neural Network will be used

Convolutional Neural Network:

- They are used to analyse visual imagery.
- They have applications in image and video recognition, recommender systems, image classification, image segmentation, medical image analysis, natural language processing.
- Training of CNN was performed using a Python library called Keras with Tensorflow backend

Using Machine learning a method will be developed with Python 3.9.5 using Convolutional Neural Network. By using Convolutional Neural Network, we will build a plant disease Detection model in Python.

A. Dataset

Dataset has been taken from Kaggle through Plant Village and machine has been trained

- <https://www.kaggle.com/lextoubourou/plantvillageapplecolor>
- <https://www.kaggle.com/emmarex/plantdiseases>

List of publicly available plant leaf dataset:

Dataset Name	URL
Plant Village	https://www.plantvillage.org/
Plant Image Analysis	https://www.plant-image-analysis.org/dataset
DATA.GOV	https://www.catalog.data.gov/dataset
UCT Machine Learning Repository	https://www.archives.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/plants
Flavia	https://www.flavia.sourceforge.net
Image Database of Plant Disease Symptoms (PDDB)	https://www.digitaphos-rep.anptia.embrop.br/
Swedish Leaf Dataset	https://www.cvl.isy.liu.se
Plant Phenotyping dataset	https://plant-phenotyping.org/dataset

Figure 2. URL for Plant disease dataset

Figure 3 shows the screenshot from Kaggle from where dataset is taken to train the model, its shows data related to apple. Figure 4 shows screenshot from Kaggle of Plant Village which has numerous data related to identification of plant disease.

Figure 3. Snapshot from Kaggle

Figure 4. Snapshot from Kaggle(PlantVillage)

```
PlantVillage
├── Pepper_bell_Bacterial_spot
├── Pepper_bell_healthy
├── Potato_Early_blight
├── Potato_Late_blight
├── Potato_healthy
├── Tomato_Bacterial_spot
├── Tomato_Early_blight
├── Tomato_Late_blight
├── Tomato_Leaf_Mold
├── Tomato_Septoria_leaf_spot
├── Tomato_Spider_mites_Two_spotted_spider_mite
├── Tomato_Target_Spot
├── Tomato_Tomato_YellowLeaf_Curl_Virus
├── Tomato_Tomato_mosaic_virus
└── Tomato_healthy
```

Figure 5. training of dataset to the model using python

B. Necessary packages imported

- 1) Numpy : a library for the Python programming language, adding support for large, multi-dimensional arrays and matrices, along with a large collection of high-level mathematical functions to operate on these arrays. (Source : Wikipedia)
- 2) Sklearn : a free software machine learning library for the Python programming language. It features various classification, regression and clustering algorithms including support vector machines, random forests, gradient boosting, k-means and DBSCAN, and is designed to interoperate with the Python numerical and scientific libraries NumPy and SciPy. (Source : Wikipedia)
- 3) Keras : Keras is an open source neural network library written in Python. It is capable of running on top of TensorFlow, Microsoft Cognitive Toolkit, or Theano. Designed to enable fast experimentation with deep neural networks, it focuses on being user-friendly, modular, and extensible. (Source : Wikipedia)
- 4) Matplotlib : a plotting library for the Python programming language and its numerical mathematics extension.

C. Image Analysis for Disease Detection in Plant

Below is the flow how image captured can be analysed for identifying plant disease on the basis of trained dataset to the model.

Figure 6. General Workflow of Plant disease Prediction Model

D. Workflow

In fig 6 general workflow of plant disease prediction model can be seen. It is described below in detail:

- 1) Image Acquisition: The image acquisition process is the first stage in the process of image analysis. It is also known as digital image acquisition. It can be defined as the visual character of an object can be represented as a digitally encoded one. In simple terms, it can be defined as an image captured using a camera. Nowadays digital image is extended to a mobile phone it makes the process of image acquisition a user-friendly.
- 2) Image Preprocessing: In the pre-processing of the image, there are two types in it namely digital image processing and analog image processing. Removal of unwanted features in the image is the main process involved in it. More algorithms are used for the removal of unwanted features in the image.
- 3) Image Segmentation: Separating image into pixel and their similar attributes is

image segmentation. It mainly helps in the image interpretation. It transfers the low-level image into a high-level image. While analyzing an image its success mainly depends on reliability in the segmentation process. Segmentation process involves both contextual and non-contextual. Several algorithms are used for the segmentation process.

- 4) Feature Extraction: A copy of the original feature is kept during the feature selection process. In the feature extraction process, new sets of features are created and these two processes mainly deal with removing unwanted noise in the image and choosing the needed features only for the image analysis process. Transformation of the attribute process takes place during the feature extraction process. The speed and effectiveness of the process are enhanced during this process.
- 5) Classification: During the classification process, the data are categorized into a number of classes. If new observation came into the process, then identifying whether the new observation belongs to which class. There are several classification algorithms available for the process of classification which gives accurate classification result as well.

IV. CONCLUSION

Technique of machine learning and neural network can be of great help for agriculture sector. Farmers can have great benefits from such latest technologies, which can help them to be future ready and also, they can go for proper management which improve their efficiency.

REFERENCES

- [1] "Implementation of artificial intelligence in agriculture for optimisation of irrigation and application of pesticides and herbicides" Tanha Talaviyaa, Dhara Shaha, Nivedita Patel, Hiteshri Yagnik, Manan Shahd
- [2] "Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture : Using Modern Day AI to Solve Traditional Farming Problems" <https://www.analyticsvidhya.com/blog/2020/11/artificial-intelligence-in-agriculture-using-modern-day-ai-to-solve-traditional-farming-problems/>
- [3] <https://www.greatdataminds.com/insights/machine-learning-in-agriculture-how-ai-helps-solve-the-industrys-most-pressing-challenges/>
- [4] "Artificial Intelligence in the Agri-Food System: Rethinking Sustainable Business Models in the COVID-19 Scenario", Assunta Di Vaio , Flavio Boccia , Loris Landriani and Rosa Palladino
- [5] "Machine Learning in Agriculture: A Review" Konstantinos G. Liakos, Patrizia Busato, Dimitrios Moshou, Simon Pearson and Dionysis Bochtis
- [6] "Image-Based Plant Disease Identification by Deep Learning Meta-Architectures" Muhammad Hammad Saleem, Sapna Khanchi, Johan Potgieter and Khalid Mahmood Arif.
- [7] "Plant Disease Detection Using Machine Learning" Shima Ramesh; Ramachandra Hebbar; Niveditha M.; Pooja R.; Prasad Bhat N.; Shashank N.; Vinod P.V.
- [8] "Crop Disease Detection Using Machine Learning and Computer Vision" <https://www.kdnuggets.com/2020/06/crop-disease-detection-computer-vision.html>
- [9] "Plant Leaf Disease Detection Using Machine Learning" Jay Trivedi, Yash Shamnani, Ruchi Gajjar
- [10] "Plant Disease Detection Using Machine Learning Algorithms" P. Prathush, K. E. Srinivasa Murthy, K. Srinivas